

Dorsal-contact architecture for cockroach monitoring: laboratory bioassays and residential field observations on capture performance

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Abstract

Early detection of domestic cockroach infestations is important in cockroach monitoring programs. Sticky traps are often used for this purpose, but they differ in architecture and in the position of the adhesive surface. This article synthesizes three reports evaluating a cockroach trap that adheres cockroaches by their dorsal cuticle (dorsal-contact trap) and compares its capture performance with that of other products. These reports include a comparison between a dorsal-contact trap and an adhesive trap with glue on the floor and tarsal contact for capturing *Periplaneta americana*. Another report compares the dorsal-contact trap with insecticidal bait stations against *Blattella germanica* and *Periplaneta americana*. Finally, a residential field deployment in Florida compares the dorsal-contact trap with a tarsal-contact trap.

Across these reports, the dorsal-contact trap showed high capture/trapping proportions within 16 to 72 hours (values reported according to the studies and species): depending on the study, 85-88% and 93-94% for *P. americana*; 93-100% for *B. germanica*.

In residential field tests in Florida, both trap types had 74% occupancy. Total cockroach captures were 2891 for the dorsal-contact model (n=87 traps) and 1848 for the tarsal-contact model (n=90 traps). Both trap types also captured other household arthropods.

Taken together, these data support the relevance of mechanical trapping by dorsal contact as a monitoring tool.

Keywords: cockroach; *Blattella germanica*; *Periplaneta americana*; adhesive trap; dorsal contact; mechanical trapping; insecticidal bait; early detection; field deployment

1. Introduction

Cockroaches are among the most ecologically and medically important urban pests worldwide. *Blattella germanica* (German cockroach) and *Periplaneta americana* (American cockroach) are major domestic species in temperate and tropical urban environments, infesting residential buildings, hospitals, restaurants, and food-processing facilities (Bell & Adiyodi, 1982; Rust et al., 1991). Their public-health impact is substantial: cockroach body parts, feces, and saliva contain potent allergens associated with asthma and allergic sensitization (Arruda et al., 2001; Pomés et al., 2017). Rabito et al. (2017) further showed that reducing cockroach exposure with insecticidal bait in the home was associated with reduced asthma morbidity in sensitized children. Moreover, cockroaches are recognized as mechanical carriers of a wide range of microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and helminths, although the epidemiological importance of this carriage varies by context.

Early detection of infestations is important. Populations of roaches can increase rapidly under favorable conditions, and infestations may become substantial before occupants notice them, because cockroaches spend much of their time hidden in harborages (Illinois Department of Public Health, 2010). Monitoring traps are therefore central tools for detection, population assessment, and evaluation of control interventions. A trap that captures a large proportion of the accessible population quickly may provide an earlier operational signal of infestation and support earlier intervention.

Conventional flat traps immobilize insects through tarsal contact with a horizontal adhesive surface. An alternative design strategy exploits the strong tendency of cockroaches to seek dark, enclosed spaces (Bell & Adiyodi, 1982), causing insects to enter traps where they ultimately become stuck by the dorsal side. This “dorsal-contact” architecture is intended to increase the probability of sustained immobilization. Indeed, dorsal adhesion is expected to limit escape more effectively, whereas tarsal adhesion affecting only one leg may still allow detachment or locomotion using the remaining legs.

This article synthesizes three data sources evaluating the dorsal-contact trap in laboratory bioassays and in a residential field deployment in Florida. Two of these sources are third-party laboratory reports, and the field deployment is an internal field report. Together, they provide complementary but non-equivalent lines of evidence on capture performance.

All reports cited in this article are included in the appendices. However, product names have been omitted from the appended reports.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Products evaluated

- Dorsal-contact adhesive trap, with an inclined roof whose inner surface is highly adhesive. No insecticide; no chemical attractant. This trap is protected by patent.
- Comparator “insecticidal bait station” A: commercial bait station used against *B. germanica* in study 19/263.
- Comparator “insecticidal bait station” B: commercial bait station used against *P. americana* in study 19/263.
- Tarsal-contact adhesive trap A: flat glue trap used as the laboratory comparator in study BIO014a-18. The adhesive is located on the floor of the trap.
- Tarsal-contact adhesive trap B: flat adhesive trap used as the field comparator during the Florida deployment.

2.2 Study 1 — Report BIO014a-18 (2018)

Comparison of the dorsal-contact trap versus the tarsal-contact trap for capturing *Periplaneta americana*. Arenas: 1 m × 1 m plastic arenas, with vertical walls coated with talc; a harborage on one side. Twenty cockroaches per arena (5 males, 5 females, 10 nymphs, 3rd to 5th instar). Cockroaches acclimated for 1 h; the two traps were then placed simultaneously in the same arena. Food was placed at the center. Three replicates; trap positions were rotated between arenas. Temperature: 24–25°C; RH: 75–80%. Assessments at 24 h and 72 h.

2.3 Study 3 — Report 19/263 (2019)

Comparison of the dorsal-contact trap with insecticidal bait stations against *B. germanica* and *P. americana*. Arenas: ~1 m × 1 m. Population: 20 per arena (2 adult males, 2 adult females, 16 mixed-

instar nymphs). Food and water placed at the center. Four replicates per treatment per species (24 tests in total). Conditions: 27.9–33.4°C; 33.3–59.8% RH; photoperiod 18:6 L:D.

Assessments at 24, 48, and 72 h. Evaluation of: % trapped (adhesive trap); % affected (knockdown + moribund + dead; bait stations).

2.4 Study 4 — Residential deployment in Florida (2019)

Sequential residential field deployment in Florida, USA. Comparison between the dorsal-contact trap (n=87) and tarsal-contact adhesive trap B (n=90). Dorsal-contact traps were analyzed immediately after opening; sticky tarsal-contact traps were analyzed by the same person from high-resolution photographs. Cockroaches were identified to species level. Outcomes: % occupied traps, total captures, mean per trap, mean per occupied trap, maximum per trap.

3. Results

3.1 Report BIO014a-18 (2018): dorsal-contact trap vs. tarsal-contact trap (*P. americana*)

Table 1. Capture results from the study (*P. americana*; 3 replicates; 20 individuals/arena). * = value derived by difference at 24 h (trap not opened).

Replicate	Dorsal-contact trap 24 h (%)	Dorsal-contact trap 72 h (%)	Tarsal-contact trap A 24 h / 72 h (%)
1	95	95	5 / 5
2	85	85	15 / 15
3	75	85	20 / 15
Mean (± SD)	85 ± 10*	88 ± 6	13 ± 8 / 12 ± 6

The dorsal-contact trap captured a mean of 85% (±10) at 24 h and 88% (±6) at 72 h. The tarsal-contact trap captured 13% (±8) at 24 h and 12% (±6) at 72 h.

3.2 Report 19/263 (2019)

Table 2. Percentage trapped (dorsal-contact trap) and affected (insecticidal bait) in report 19/263 (mean ± SE; n=4 replicates).

Species	24 h trapped (%)	72 h trapped (%)	Insecticide 72 h affected (%)	Certification
<i>B. germanica</i>	93.4 ± 5.0	100.0 ± 0.0	71.3 ± 2.4	GLP / ORETO 418
<i>P. americana</i>	93.6 ± 3.9	93.6 ± 3.3	67.5 ± 9.7	GLP / ORETO 418

The dorsal-contact trap trapped 93.4% of *B. germanica* and 93.6% of *P. americana* at 24 hours. At 72 hours, 100% of *B. germanica* and 93.6% of *P. americana* were trapped. The insecticidal bait produced 71.3% “affected” (knockdown + moribund + dead) for *B. germanica* and 67.5% for *P. americana* at 72 hours.

3.3 Residential deployment in Florida (2019)

Table 3. Cockroach capture results from the Florida residential field deployment (2019).

Metric	Dorsal-contact trap (n=87)	Flat competitor trap (n=90)
Occupied traps (%)	74%	74%
Actual cockroaches	2891	1848
Mean per trap	33.2 ± 141.9	21.2 ± 70.4

Mean per occupied trap	99.7 ± 234.5	45.1 ± 97.8
Maximum in one trap	1113	372

Both trap models had identical occupancy (74%). The dorsal-contact trap series captured 2891 cockroaches in total across 87 traps, versus 1848 across 90 tarsal-contact B traps—a ratio of about 1.6:1 despite three fewer traps. The maximum capture in a single trap was 1113 (dorsal contact) versus 372 (tarsal contact). Three species were identified: *B. germanica* (dominant; 2846 dorsal contact / 1790 flat adhesive), *Periplaneta fuliginosa*, and *Blattella asahinai*. Dorsal-contact traps also captured non-target nuisance arthropods.

4. Discussion

4.1 Importance of early detection

High-performance monitoring traps are a cornerstone of early cockroach detection. A trap that captures a large fraction of the accessible population within the first 24 hours may provide an earlier operational infestation signal. This matters because *B. germanica* populations can increase rapidly, and cockroach allergen exposure tends to rise with infestation intensity (Arruda et al., 2001; Pomés et al., 2017). Earlier detection may therefore support earlier intervention, although this article does not directly measure allergen reduction or clinical benefit.

The current data indicate high capture/trapping proportions for the dorsal-contact trap under the reported laboratory conditions, particularly within the first 24 to 72 hours.

4.2 Advantage of dorsal contact vs. tarsal contact

Report BIO014a-18 provides a direct laboratory comparison between the two adhesive architectures: the dorsal-contact trap achieved 85% and 88% capture at 24 h and 72 h, respectively, versus 13% and 12% for the tarsal-contact trap. Under these tested laboratory conditions, the dorsal-contact design was associated with higher capture.

4.3 Traps vs. bait stations: speed, safety, and resistance

In the reported studies, the dorsal-contact trap showed high capture proportions within 24 to 72 hours, whereas insecticidal bait stations rely on ingestion and a delay before observable effects appear, depending on the endpoint used. During this delay, non-trapped cockroaches may remain mobile. This comparison should nevertheless be interpreted cautiously because the endpoints differ (trapped/immobilized vs. affected/dead).

A potential advantage of physical traps is that they do not rely on an insecticidal mode of action and are therefore not directly subject to physiological insecticide resistance. Scharf and Gondhalekar (2021) reviewed the evolution, mechanisms, and management implications of insecticide resistance in German cockroaches. An adhesive device may nonetheless remain sensitive to behavioral factors (avoidance, trajectory) and environmental factors (dust, humidity) that affect the probability of capture.

4.4 Field deployment

The residential deployment in Florida provides an important field-based complement to the laboratory reports because it reflects real residential conditions rather than arena assays. In these trap series, total captures were higher in dorsal-contact traps (about 1.6-fold), and the maximum capture per trap reached 1113. These observations support the practical importance of the Florida report and are consistent with high capture capacity in at least some infestation contexts, while still requiring interpretation in light of the sequential design and the different counting methods.

5. Limitations

- Non-equivalent endpoints between product categories: “trapped/immobilized” (traps) vs. “affected” or “dead” (baits)(Report 19/263).
- Limited sample size in some trials (e.g., n=3 replicates): results should be interpreted as descriptive/exploratory (BIO014a-18)
- Florida deployment: different counting methods (direct vs. photographic).
- Generalization: arena conditions and tested strains may not represent all field contexts; adhesive performance may vary with dust/humidity.

6. Conclusion

The dorsal-contact trap shows, in the reported studies, high immobilization/capture proportions for *B. germanica* and *P. americana* over 16 to 72 hours. In report BIO014a-18, the captured proportion is higher than that of an adhesive trap based on tarsal contact under the tested laboratory conditions. In report 19/263, high trapping proportions are reported at 24-72 h, whereas bait stations are reported as ‘% affected’; these endpoints are not directly comparable.

The residential deployment in Florida reports identical occupancy (74%) for the two brands, with higher total captures in the dorsal-contact series.

Overall, these data support the relevance of mechanical trapping by dorsal-contact architecture as a monitoring tool. The Florida field deployment remains an important but methodologically limited component of this evidence base because it documents performance under residential conditions; however, simultaneous comparative field trials with harmonized counting methods would be needed before drawing broader conclusions about relative efficacy.

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Conflict of interest

The corresponding author is affiliated with InnoC SRL, the company that developed and commercializes the dorsal-contact trap evaluated in this article. The field deployment report (Study 4) was produced internally by Domobios SA. The two laboratory reports (BIO014a-18 and 19/263) were conducted by independent third-party organizations.